

Diversified rotations in protected vegetable production systems including cover crops

Problem

In protected vegetable systems of the Mediterranean area, cover crops can offer different ecosystem services. However, in practice, their inclusion in rotations is limited because the land use is primarily driven by profitability objectives.

Solution

Based on the ROTAT+ modelling tool (Dogliotti et al. 2003), several rotations including cover crops were generated and have been subject to a procedure of multi-objectives optimisation and assessment.

Outcome

For long rotations (here 5 years) that respect minimum period repeats by species and botanical family, cover crops (up to 3 in 5 years) can be included with little or no impact on gross margin at rotation level as shown in multi-criteria assessment results (Figure 1).

Applicability box

Theme

Rotation, Multiple cropping, assessment, cropping system

Geographical coverage

Mediterranean area

Application time

Duration of the rotation

Required time

Duration of the rotation

Period of impact

Duration of the rotation

Equipment

High plastic tunnels

Best in

Middle-sized diversified farms targeting long and short supply chains.

Figure 1: Mean annual margins of rotations generated with ROTAT+ as a function of the number of hours needed in the field.

Blue lines: the zone where the rotations without cover crops are located. Orange triangles: examples of rotations from the optimisation procedure that include one to three cover crops.

For A, B and C, the optimisation procedure was based on margin, labour, organic matter balance and soil use intensity, and refined by the number of cover crops and different crops. For D, a rentability criteria (margin/labour) was included instead of soil use intensity.

Practical recommendation

Year	I												II												III												IV												V																																																																																																											
Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12																																																																																																
B													Celeri stick												French bean												Kohlrabi												S. pepper												Mini-chard												Zucchini												SPB																																																																							
A	Kohlrabi Eggplant												Onion												Cucumber												SPB												Mini-chard												Onion												Tomato												Kohlrabi												French bean												Celeri stick												Zucchini												SPB																							
B													French bean												Celeri stick												Zucchini												SPB												Kohlrabi												Tomato												Onion												Cucumber												SPB																																															
C	Cucumber												SPB												Mini-chard												French bean												Rye-vetch												S. pepper												Celeri stick												Cauliflower												SPB												Salad												Kohlrabi												Tomato												Onion											
D	Kohlrabi Eggplant												Onion												Cucumber												SPB												Kohlrabi												B.m												Mini-chard												Celeri stick												Zucchini												SPB																																															
													Mini-chard												Celeri stick												Zucchini												SPB												Onion												Kohlrabi												Cucumber												SPB																																																											
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Figure 2: Examples of diversified rotations including cover crops. Cover crops are outlined in black; SPB: mixture of sorghum-pea-buckwheat, B.m: brown mustard. Rotations A, B and D each include different options but with similar results.

The rotations displayed in Figure 2 include one to three periods of cover crops with a maximum of two types of cover crops. Mixtures of species (rye-vetch or sorghum-pea-buckwheat) are chosen to optimise soil resources.

The two types of cover crops included represent three different planting periods (autumn, spring and summer) in order to favour crop diversity at the rotation scale and to propose different options to be adapted according to farm objectives and constraints.

Cover crops can meet different objectives depending on soil history such as increasing soil health, limiting the development of a given pest (biodisinfection) and managing weed stock. At farm scale, constraints can include the priority of maintaining a significant proportion of crops and freeing up time in a given period.

It should be noted that the impact on different indicator assessments depends on the composition of the whole rotation and not only on the frequency or type of cover crops. For instance, for a level of margin similar to rotation B, rotation D is characterised by a much lower work time (Figure 1) but also by a lower use of fertilisation, water and crop protection inputs.

Further information

Further readings

Dogliotti S., Rossing W.A.H., van Ittersum M.K. European Journal of Agronomy 19 (2003) 239-250

Perrin B., Lefèvre A., 2021. Multi-species SPB summer cover crop in protected vegetable systems. DiverIMPACTS Practice Abstract

About this practice abstract and DiverIMPACTS

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DiverIMPACTS: The project is running from June 2017 to May 2022. The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability - is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

Project website: www.diverimpacts.net

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